

Klein-Gordon Equation and Stochasticity

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The Klein-Gordon equation is often created by taking the deterministic relativistic invariant $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$), replacing E with $E-V(x)$, $E = \partial/\partial t$ and p with $-i\partial/\partial x$ and having the derivatives act on a function $W(x,t)$. This seems to suggest that the starting point is deterministic classical mechanics (special relativistic form) E, p equation with stochasticity somehow introduced by having average E and p follow from the action of the operators $\partial/\partial t$ and $-i\partial/\partial x$ on a stochastic function $W(x,t)$. It also makes it somewhat difficult to understand, from first principles, why one would create a linear equation in E, p (compatible with $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$), i.e. the Dirac equation.

We suggest that the entire approach to Klein-Gordon equation is stochastic, with the $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ equation appearing as an invariant expression of average values which describes motion as seen from different frames moving with constant average velocity v . In such a case, one is not limited to the form $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ and there is nothing unusual about trying to create an equation linear in E and p . In particular, we argue that the free particle form $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ follows from two separate maximizations of Shannon's entropy subject to complex constraints (for periodicity). As a result, free motion with a constant E and p is already stochastic as seen from a photon moving in a region with an index of refraction n or a particle moving in a region with constant potential. Changing to a potential $V(x)$ leads to the notion of an average kinetic energy because a constant p is associated with a distribution in x i.e. $\exp(ipx)$.

One may think in terms of these average values in order to consider frames moving with constant v . This leads to both $-Et + px$ and $E^2 - p^2 = m^2$ being invariants. If a $V(x)$ is present, one may replace E with $E-V(x)$, but then needs a statistical average $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to describe p . The time portion may still be $\exp(-iEt)$ if one has a bound system characterized by a single average energy. This yields the Klein-Gordon equation. There is, however, no particular reason why one could not use an equation linear in E and p (consistent with $E^2 - p^2 = m^2$), because the latter follows from the average v (deterministic view) of the stochastic $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ two-dimensional probability.

Special Relativity and the Maximization of Shannon's Entropy

We argued in (1) that one may perform two maximizations of Shannon's entropy subject to complex constraints (for periodicity) linked to E and p . The motivation for this approach is the one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon moving along the x direction in a medium with index of refraction $n_1=1$ into medium $n_2>n_1$ with an interface along the y axis at $x=0$. We argue that the motion of the photon, although looking smooth with a momentum p_n and a velocity c/n , is really stochastic because it interacts with the various atoms in the medium. As a result, p_n and c/n are only average values. A main point we wish to make is that one cannot find the relative probabilities of reflection/refraction unless one uses a description of the stochasticity in the medium. In particular, one uses $\exp(ipx)$ and writes a continuity equation as well as a balance of p equation. One may note, however, that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$, giving the semblance of smooth average motion. Thus we argue that even a constant p may be associated with

probabilistic motion in x . A similar argument may then apply for E and t . P and E represent different kinds of physical interactions. The former represents target collisions which change p , while the latter represent interactions which change E , i.e. climbing a potential hill or falling down.

As a result, we suggest, as in (1), that one might try to maximize Shannon's entropy in order to find probability distributions in x and t for constant p and E .

Maximize: $P(x) \ln(P(x)) + i p x P(x)$ ((1a)) and $P(t) \ln(P(t)) - i E t P(t)$ ((1b))

The "i" is used to ensure a periodic result. The solutions are: $\exp(ipx)$ ((2a)) and $\exp(-iEt)$ ((2b)) where we have placed a minus in front of E so that: $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ has a constant phase when $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$.

The consequences of ((2a)) and ((2b)) are that there are probability distributions in x and t . Thus one may speak of an average velocity, but stochasticity is present. Even for a photon interacting stochastically with atoms in a medium with index of refraction n , motion is smooth on average and the photon travels a certain distance in a certain amount of time. (One, however, cannot drop the notion of stochastic motion as it is needed to solve for the probabilities of one dimensional reflection-refraction. This solution cannot be found using average values.)

$\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ seem to indicate that there exists stochastic behaviour even if a particle or photon moves in a vacuum. Let E may be associated with a $V(x)$ which is a potential which changes in x . How does this potential affect momentum? Experimentally a particle slows down as it loses potential energy suggesting that its momentum should also be less. Momentum, however, is associated with a distribution $\exp(ipx)$ in x space. Thus even though a kinetic energy $KE(x)$ may decrease with each x point, one cannot associate a constant p with each x . It seems that an interaction with a $V(x)$ must be described in terms of a statistical average i.e.

$$KE(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, the stochasticity of a constant p , $\exp(ipx)$, forces the notion of an average kinetic energy. Even if one were given a $V(x)$, based on an experimental measurement, how does one use $V(x)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ in an equation? We argue that such an equation may follow from considering different frames moving with constant average v .

Special Relativity from Maximization of Shannon's Entropy

We argue that maximization of Shannon's entropy leads to ((2a)) and ((2b)). Multiplying these together yields $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. We note that $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$ leaves $-Et+px$ constant. What if one views this phase from a frame moving at constant average velocity? We argue that $-Et+px$ should be an invariant based on the idea that the probability should be the same. Thus: $-E't'+p'x' = -Et+px$. Using the idea that $v=x/t$, one may find (as in (1)) the transformation which expresses (x',t') or (p',E') in terms of (x,t) and (p,E) . One may also show that: $E = \text{mocc} / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p = \text{mov} / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Not only is $-Et+px$ an invariant, but also:

$-E^2 + p^2 = \text{constant} = m^2 c^4$ considering $p=0$ and $E=mc^2$ in a rest frame. ((4))

One may note that one deals with smooth v, p and E , here so these are treated as deterministic values. In actuality, one has $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ and cannot have a particle at $x=0$, for example. Thus ((4)) is an average equation. Is this a problem? It seems to be fine in the sense that we argue one needs to use an average to calculate kinetic energy(x). Thus one may use an average to express p^2 if a $V(x)$ is present and E as well. How does one incorporate $V(x)$? We suggest, as done often in the literature, that one may replace E with $E-V(x)$. If one considers a bound state, then one may have a single E associated with $\exp(-iEt)$. Then:

$-(E-V(x))(E-V(x)) + \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2 \ \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \} = m^2 c^4$ ((5))

((5)) is the Klein-Gordon equation. One may write E as $i \partial / \partial t \exp(-iEt)$ and $p^2 \exp(ipx)$ as $-\partial^2 / \partial x^2 \exp(ipx)$ so ((5)) becomes:

$-(i \partial / \partial t - V(x))(i \partial / \partial t - V(x)) - \partial^2 / \partial x^2 \ W(x) / W(x) = m^2 c^4$ ((6))

In other words, the expression $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ follows from considerations of averages based on the invariance of the argument of $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. It is not an a priori fundamental equation separated from the stochastic $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$, rather it is an average statement, which takes on a deterministic sense, we argue. One might also consider different expressions, say a linear expression in $E-V(x)$ and p average which is consistent with ((6)). In particular, one could first consider the case of a free particle with $V(x)=0$, but p still linked with $\exp(ipx)$ and E with $\exp(-iEt)$.

If $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ were a fundamental equation, there would seem to be no justification for searching for other forms, but it is just an average invariance statement. There could be other equations consistent with it. As a result, we argue that the linear differential Dirac equation, which is consistent with $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ seems to be completely normal.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that a constant p (momentum) and E energy are associated with stochastic motion in a medium (for example one with an index of refraction) or even a vacuum. As a result, we perform two maximizations of Shannon's entropy, one for $P(x)$ the other for $P(t)$, subject to the constraint $i p x P(x)$ and $-i E t P(t)$. The "i" ensures periodicity and the minus sign associated with E ensures the product solution: $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ has a phase which is unchanged when: $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$ and $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$. We further suggest that this result must hold in any frame moving at an average velocity v .

Thus $-Et + px$ is an invariant when seen from frames moving at constant average v . The idea of an average v means that one has dropped stochasticity and is viewing things in a deterministic manner. Given this point of view, one may obtain the form of the transformation of (x,t) and (p,E) as seen in a frame moving with average velocity $-v$ (see (1) for details). As a result, considering the argument of the probabilistic $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ in terms of average v (determinism), one obtains special relativity. One must keep in mind, however, that one cannot abandon the probabilistic

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ form and only work with deterministic averages for at least two reasons. First, experimentally, there exists n-slit interference-diffraction. Secondly, one cannot solve a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem without using the stochastic $\exp(ipx)$. Average values are not sufficient.

A dilemma seems to occur if one considers a potential function $V(x)$ which may “consume” kinetic energy. In other words, $KE(x)$, but a constant p is associated with a distribution in x . As a result of the stochasticity of $\exp(ipx)$, it seems one may only describe kinetic energy in terms of an average using $\exp(ipx)$ s. This still begs the question: What equation containing E , p and $V(x)$ should one use? Given that one takes averages of any function of p , one may look for an average equation. $-Et+px = \text{constant}$ is one such equation as is $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). This latter is the equation one wants if one changes E to $E-V(x)$. “ p^2 ” must then be replaced with an average, i.e. $\frac{\sum_p a(p) p^2 \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)}$, but E may be left as a constant for a bound system. This then leads to the Klein-Gordon equation. Thus the form $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ is not a fundamental deterministic equation, but rather an average result based on the form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and invariance of physics as seen from frames moving at constant average velocities. In principle, one could look for another equation, say linear in E , p for a free particle, but consistent with $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$, which is what Dirac.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Stochasticity at a Single Particle Level? (preprint,zenodo, 2023)